

D1.2 AN ONTOLOGY FOR DIGITAL TWIN MODELS FOR THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

This deliverable describes the ontology suite which will form the basis for the ASHVIN digital twin platform. The ontological model conceptualizes physical objects, the environment on the construction site, and their virtual replicas to enable accurate version, configuration, and state management for a real-time construction digital twin. Additionally, the ontology suite will encompass the entire lifecycle for a civil infrastructure i.e., design, construction and operation. The document primarily comprises of three ontologies ConDT, DesDT & OpDT for the construction, design, and operation phases respectively for a built infrastructure's digital twin.

KEYWORDS

Digital twin, Infrastructure lifecycle, Ontology, Knowledge domain, Conceptualization,

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ACRONYMS & DEFINITIONS

AEC	Architecture, Engineering, and Construction
BIM	Building Information Model
ConDT	Construction digital twin ontology
CQs	Competency questions
DesDT	Design digital twin ontology
DT	Digital twin
IDM	Information Delivery Manuals
IoT	Internet of Things
KPIs	Key performance indicators
LOD	Level of detail
OpDT	Operation digital twin ontology
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PI	Performance indicator
SAREF	Smart Applications REFerence ontology
WP	Work Package

ASHVIN PROJECT

ASHVIN aims at enabling the European construction industry to significantly improve its productivity, while reducing cost and ensuring absolutely safe work conditions, by providing a proposal for a European wide digital twin standard, an open-source digital twin platform integrating IoT and image technologies, and a set of tools and demonstrated procedures to apply the platform and the standard proven to guarantee specified productivity, cost, and safety improvements. The envisioned platform will provide a digital representation of the construction product at hand and allow to collect real-time digital data before, during, and after production of the product to continuously monitor changes in the environment and within the production process. Based on the platform, ASHVIN will develop and demonstrate applications that use the digital twin data. These applications will allow it to fully leverage the potential of the IoT based digital twin platform to reach the expected impacts (better scheduling forecast by 20%; better allocation of resources and optimization of equipment usage; reduced number of accidents; reduction of construction projects). The ASHVIN solutions will overcome worker protection and privacy issues that come with the tracking of construction activities, provide means to fuse video data and sensor data, integrate geo-monitoring data, provide multi-physics simulation methods for digital representing the behavior of a product (not only its shape), provide evidence based engineering methods to design for productivity and safety, provide 4D simulation and visualization methods of construction processes, and develop a lean planning process supported by real-time data. All innovations will be demonstrated on real-world construction projects across Europe. The ASHVIN consortium combines strong R&I players from 9 EU member states with strong expertise in construction and engineering management, digital twin technology, IoT, and data security / privacy.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	INTRODUCTION	9
1.1	Background	9
1.2	Objective of the Deliverable	9
1.3	Intended Audience.....	10
1.4	Relation to other Tasks and Deliverables	10
1.5	Workflow and outline of deliverable	11
2	LITERATURE REVIEW.....	12
2.1	Knowledge Representation for Digital Twins.....	12
2.2	Ontology-based modelling in AEC Industry	12
2.3	Knowledge Representation for Construction Digital Twin.....	12
2.4	Ontologies for an Infrastructure’s Lifecycle	13
3	METHODOLOGY.....	15
3.1	Ontology Specification	15
3.2	Knowledge Acquisition and Conceptualization.....	16
4	INFRADT	17
4.1	Construction DT ontology (ConDT).....	17
4.1.1	Built Environment.....	18
4.1.2	Digital Asset	23
4.1.3	Data Resources	25
4.1.4	Processes	26
4.1.4.1	Site Monitoring.....	26
4.1.4.2	Lean Planning	27
4.1.4.3	Configuration Management	30
4.1.4.4	Risk Management.....	30
4.1.5	Outcomes	31
4.2	Design DT ontology (DesDT)	33
4.2.1	Processes	33
4.2.1.1	Evidence-based Design	34

4.2.1.2	Generative Design	35
4.2.1.3	4D Planning Visualization	37
4.2.2	Outcomes	37
4.3	Operation DT ontology (OpDT)	40
4.3.1	Processes	40
4.3.1.1	Structural Health Monitoring (SHM)	41
4.3.1.2	Multi-Physics Calibration.....	42
4.3.2	Outcomes	43
5	ONTOLOGY EVALUATION	45
5.1	Workshop with experts	45
5.2	Ontology design verification.....	46
6	STRUCTURED VOCABULARY AND APIS	47
7	CONCLUSION.....	49
8	OUTLOOK	50
	REFERENCES	51
	APPENDIX- ONTOLOGIES HIERARCHY AND PROPERTIES	54
	ConDT Ontology hierarchy	54
	ConDT property hierarchies	56
	Standards.....	57

INDEX OF FIGURES

Figure 1: D1.2 integration with other WPs.....	11
Figure 2: D1.2 workflow	11
Figure 3: Envisioned data flow for ASHVIN platform.....	15
Figure 4: InfraDT suite with phase-wise lifecycle representation	17
Figure 5: ConDT ontology and its sub-classes.....	18
Figure 6: Aspects of an object (IEC 81346)	18
Figure 7: BuiltEnvironment class and knowledge blocks for different aspects	20
Figure 8: Product (Roof Window) represented as per the ETIM taxonomy	21
Figure 9: Product (Culvert) represent as per ETIM taxonomy	22
Figure 10: Product (Crane) represent as per ETIM taxonomy	22
Figure 11: DigitalAsset class representation	23
Figure 12: Level of information need framework	24
Figure 13: Overview of SAREF ontology.....	25
Figure 14: DataResources class and knowledge block for different dimensions	26
Figure 15: Processes representation for a construction DT	26
Figure 16: SiteMonitoring process ontology	28
Figure 17: Lean Planning process ontology	29
Figure 18: CM process ontology.....	30
Figure 19: Risk Management ontology.....	31
Figure 20: DT-related outcomes during the construction phase	32
Figure 21: DesDT ontology and its classes.	33
Figure 22: Processes representation for a DT during the design phase.....	33
Figure 23: Overview of the ontology for evidence-based design.	34
Figure 24: Generative design process ontology.....	36
Figure 25: 4DV-D process ontology	37
Figure 26: DT-based outcomes during the design phase	39
Figure 27: OpDT ontology and its classes.	40
Figure 28: Processes representation for a DT during the maintenance/operation phase.....	40
Figure 29: DT-based SHM ontology	41
Figure 30: DT-based Multiphysics ontology	42
Figure 31: DT-based outcomes during the operation/maintenance phase	44
Figure 32: ConDT ontology hierarchy 1	54
Figure 33: ConDT ontology hierarchy 2	55
Figure 34: Object property hierarchies	56

INDEX OF TABLES

Table 1: Literature sources for knowledge capturing	16
Table 2: Errors for the ConDT ontology verification	46
Table 3: Construction DT Interoperability APIs	47

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

The built environment incorporates a wide range of entities from buildings to infrastructures. The correlation of these entities is present at various scales and in multiple ways. Furthermore, the built environment also involves different stakeholders to carry out collaboration throughout the lifecycle of the entity during the design, construction, and operation phase. The major portion of this environment is governed by Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) sector. A cost-effective collaboration and seamless data flow among the various stakeholders have always been a key challenge to the industry (Pauwels et al., 2018).

Digital solutions are widely used across the construction industry focusing on automating processes across different phases of the infrastructure's lifecycle. Although these systems yield considerable improvements, they largely remain detached from one another. Digital Twins (DTs) offer coherent solutions by integrating many technologies and methodologies to create an effective living system (Boje et al., 2020). A digital twin is defined as a digital replica of a building or infrastructure system alongside possibilities to accurately simulate its multi-physics behaviour (structural, energy). Moreover, the digital twin enhances the scope to represent all important processes around the building or infrastructure system. These processes include developing design information (as-designed vs as-built) and a real-time precise replication of concerning construction and maintenance activities. The technical facilitator for such digital twin representation is the internet of things (IoT), thus enabling connections between real-time data feed from sensors and cameras with the aim of establishing a close correspondence of the physical entities and processes with their virtual replicas.

Generally, a lack of shared understanding of complex leads to inconsistencies in the identification of requirements for a system, to which one of the solutions is the development of formalized knowledge representations (Uschold and Gruninger, 1996). The term “ontology” originally refers to a branch of philosophy and involves the study of existence. Although the term is borrowed from philosophy, in terms of the information technology system, this means that anything that “exists” can be represented. An ontology essentially represents categories of things that exist or may exist in an application domain. Ontologies have been developed for efficient knowledge management including physical and abstract objects, their relations, and events influencing them (Sowa, 2000).

1.2 Objective of the Deliverable

The objective of this document is to define an ontological model for construction-centred DTs. Therefore, this deliverable report introduces a systemization of core concepts for the development of an ontology for a digital twin of an infrastructure project through its entire lifecycle in the form of an ontology suite called “InfraDT”. The developed knowledge base will serve as the basis of the ASHVIN digital twin platform. Each phase of a built infrastructure’s lifecycle (design, construction, and operation) will be explicitly modeled in the form of an ontology. Additionally, possibilities for accurate version, configuration, and state management for the ASHVIN digital twin platform are included in the ontology development.

Therefore, InfraDT encompasses concepts for DTs and their aspects during the complete lifecycle of an infrastructure project. The proposed models can be summarized as follows:

- ConDT: An ontology for the digital twin of an infrastructure during the construction phase.
- DesDT: An ontology for the digital twin of an infrastructure during the design phase.
- OpDT: An ontology for the digital twin of an infrastructure during the operation/maintenance phase.

Furthermore, the ASHVIN research project has 10 real-world projects in different phases of construction and includes buildings, foundations, bridges, and infrastructure. The developed ontology is created for a selected number of demo sites to enhance the vocabulary of the particular domain related to the demo project and enrich the potential of the ontology itself.

1.3 Intended Audience

The target audience for this deliverable primarily consists of research and development (R&D) interested parties, digital twin technology providers, IoT developers, and digital solution providers in the construction industry, alongside European standardization bodies. Alongside the ontology knowledge can be used by those involved directly in the construction industry such as construction companies and facility managers who plan to implement digital twins for their infrastructure projects.

Altogether, this research work targets to promote the understanding and systemization of knowledge involved in an infrastructure digital twin's entire lifecycle and promote further R&D by academicians and industry personnel for ontologies for digital twin in construction.

1.4 Relation to other Tasks and Deliverables

This deliverable is based on T1.2 Digital twin IoT integration, focussed on the development of required functionality on top of the IoT platform to allow tracking of device states and make simulations to create/test and construct in a virtual environment. This deliverable aims to present the ontology for the ASHVIN DT platform.

Figure 1 shows how the proposed InfraDT ontology suite consisting of various ontologies during each lifecycle supports and integrates other work packages (WPs). The Construction digital twin (ConDT) ontology is not only closely related but also developed based on concepts of WP4 for real-time construction simulation and WP3 for data fusion in real-time construction monitoring. Design digital twin ontology (DesDT) also conceptualizes knowledge on the use of DT technology at the start of the product development lifecycle i.e., the design phase thus facilitating WP2: *Design for productivity and safety*. Finally, concepts mapped by Operation/Maintenance digital twin (OpDT) cater to and use WP5 focusing on the real-time connection between physical infrastructures and their virtual models for the purpose of maintenance and asset management tasks.

Figure 1: D1.2 integration with other WPs

Also, the vocabulary developed in the ontological model T1.2 will be resourceful for T1.3 *Interoperability* presenting the Information Delivery Manuals (IDM) that will be utilized by the ASHVIN tools.

1.5 Workflow and outline of deliverable

The step-wise workflow of T1.2 is represented in Figure 2. The report comprises of eight chapters. Chapter 2 gives background information about pertinent literature for knowledge representation of digital twins and relevant ontologies. Chapter 3 summarizes the methodology adopted for ontology specification. Followed by chapter 4 presenting the “InfraDT” ontology suite. Chapter 5 presented the verification process for the developed ontology. Subsequently, chapter 6 signifies the use of structured vocabularies for the ASHVIN architecture. Lastly, chapters 7 & 8 summarize the work done and the further developments.

Figure 2: D1.2 workflow

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

This section presents previous research on digital twin knowledge representation and relevant ontology works to give a background and reference for the development of InfraDT.

2.1 Knowledge Representation for Digital Twins

Digital Twin is a term that was coined in 2003 at the University of Michigan's Executive Course on Product Lifecycle Management (Grieves, 2014). Although at that time the concept was not mature enough due to technological limitations, it has resurfaced in recent years and has become more mature and definitive as the world becomes more interconnected. Despite the fact that the concept of DT was introduced by Grieves in 2003, it was revisited by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) in 2012 defining it as "integrated multi-physics, multi-scale, probabilistic, simulation of a system that mirrors the life of its twin promptly using historical data, real-time sensor data, and available physical models". This is still the most used definition of a digital twin in academic publications (Glaessgen and Stargel, 2012).

DTs are essentially nourished by bidirectional interaction between the physical and virtual spheres and therefore establish new possibilities. Data management is decisive for the development and maintenance of any information system, DT being one such concept requires data management to address challenges such as data variety, data mining, and DT dynamics between the virtual and physical spaces (Singh et al., 2021). Ontologies as the basis for the application of semantic web and linked data technologies are a well-established approach for leveraging data and information sources (Zhong et al., 2015). An ontology supports the development of formalized knowledge representation and is essentially an explicit representation of concepts, terminologies, and relationships existing in a particular domain (Gruber, 1995). Ontologies formalize complex engineering knowledge allowing humans and computers to understand and exploit domain knowledge. Furthermore, with knowledge mapping and logic as its basis, it can assist the automation of routine engineering tasks alongside providing computational solutions to complex tasks (Hartmann and Trappey, 2020).

2.2 Ontology-based modelling in AEC Industry

Ontological modelling plays a significant role in the domain representation of the construction process. It has become evident in recent years that the development of domain ontologies in the AEC industry is vital for the development of knowledge management and integrated workflow (Zhou et al., 2016). Lima et al. (2003) introduced the e-COGNOS platform presenting the first comprehensive ontology-based portal for knowledge management in construction. Additionally, DOCK 1.0 is another example of the conceptualization of key terms in the construction domain and their relationships and behaviour with further emphasis on context for the representation of construction knowledge (El-Diraby, 2013). Researchers (Zhang et al., 2015) investigated an approach to organize, store and re-use construction safety knowledge including the Construction Safety Model with interaction with BIM also explored.

2.3 Knowledge Representation for Construction Digital Twin

The formulation of workflow for a construction-centered DT system is fragmented and is built upon fundamentals of computing in construction, construction monitoring

technologies, and lean construction (Sacks et al., 2020). Recent studies have explored data-driven representations and ontological dimensions of DTs for construction. Research by Sacks et al. (2020) introduced a conceptual evaluation of the characterization of information systems for digital twin construction (DTC) along 4 dimensions explicitly: physical-virtual, product-process, intent-status, and data information-knowledge decisions. As a result, by basic classification of information entities into virtual or physical, product or processes, and intended or realized aspects, they establish the required ontological dimensions of digital twins for construction. On the other hand, Fjeld (2020) proposed a six-level framework Digital Twin Maturity Index (DTMI) based on the degree of automation and degree of integration between the physical and virtual starting with a Static Twin (Level 100) to an Intelligent Twin at Level 500 with each level possessing the features of lower maturity levels. The contemplated incremental and data-driven approach envisions a process of learning and simulation of several scenarios to become a fully autonomous twin. Further building upon work by Fjeld, (Mêda et al., 2021) advocated the use of digital data templates (DDT) and digital building logbooks (DBL) within the framework of incremental DTC to establish maturity levels that streamline the digital transformation of construction for a circular economy. Moreover, research work done in H2020 EU projects such as COGITO present an ontology network to conceptualize the construction itself, its process, and resources to streamline interoperability for the development of the DT platform (COGITO H2020, 2021).

2.4 Ontologies for an Infrastructure's Lifecycle

Within the AEC industry, the use of semantic web technologies in the form of ontology development has increased over the years (Pauwels et al., 2018). Ontological studies have focussed on mapping knowledge discretely during the design, construction, and operational phase of an infrastructure's lifecycle. At the initial design phase, work done by Niknam and Karshenas, (2017) presents a BIM design ontology (BIMDO) approach to conceptualizing the design properties of building elements with further integration with cost-estimation and scheduling knowledge bases to create a resource use profile during the design and planning phase of an infrastructure's lifecycle. In addition, some ontologies have conceptualized the construction stage of an infrastructure's lifecycle. A recent research study by (Zheng et al., 2021) provides an example of a set of digital construction ontologies (DiCon) formalizing and integrating construction workflow domain information with data from heterogeneous sources and information systems for an organised representation of multi-context data within the digital construction context. Research by Gregor and Tibaut (2020) proposes an ontology-based method for information creation for the digital twin of buildings with its core built on the existing Building Topology Ontology (BOT). Intending to minimize human assistance and processing of raw point cloud data, the authors introduce a BOT-driven approach to translate point cloud data to ontology data (individuals and their object and data properties), which can be further formatted to establish the automated scan-to-BIM aspect for a digital twin. In addition, a study by (Liu et al., 2021) introduces the Building Concrete Monitoring (BCOM) ontology mapping the information schema for monitoring of concrete work, concrete curing, and testing of concrete properties. Furthermore, the use of an information container holding information about concrete works and linking it to the IFC-based building model enables possibilities for information flow between

the construction and operation phase for the further development of digital twin and asset management.

In the operational phase of the infrastructure, the use of an ontology to model the environment adds richness for intelligent exploitation. (Zhong et al., 2018) developed an ontology-based framework for the integration of building information from BIM, building environment monitoring through sensors, and regulatory information based on building regulation and design requirements to automate compliance checking during the monitoring phase of the building's lifecycle. Researchers (Ait-Lamallam et al., 2021) detail an ontological approach IFCInfra4OM for the standardization of road infrastructure BIM during the operation and maintenance phase of highways through the integration of monitored data into the 3D model to establish a highway information model to manage project data during the operational phase of the highway infrastructure. InfraDT envisions to conceptualize the entire lifecycle of infrastructure digital twin, but in this research study, the construction phase is given greater emphasis.

3 METHODOLOGY

InfraDT is the basis for the ASHVIN platform which represents an open-source real-time DT platform integrating IoT, image technologies, a set of tools, and demonstrated procedures aimed at productivity, cost, and safety for the European construction industry. Figure 3 represents the envisioned data mapping for the ASHVIN digital twin platform. InfraDT provides a knowledge base for the development of the ASHVIN platform and its DT toolbox. The deliverable D7.1 within the ASHVIN project gives an extensive insight into the implementation of the ASHVIN platform and tools to be validated on real-life demonstration projects.

The following subsections present comprehensive information on ontology development. The ontology development is based on the guidelines described by the METHONTOLOGY approach (Fernández-López et al., 1997) which stresses on the processes of knowledge acquisition, conceptualization, implementation, and evaluation.

Figure 3: Envisioned data flow for ASHVIN platform

3.1 Ontology Specification

The first step of ontology development is the specification phase to produce a general description of the ontology. This section gives explicit information about the aim and scope of the targeted ontologies and the intended end-users. The specification is established through a list of questions called competency questions (CQs) (Grüniger and Fox, 1995). These questions are answered using natural language.

What is the purpose? The purpose of InfraDT is to formalize concepts related to connectivity and information creation between the physical and virtual for an infrastructure DT along with the processes involved during its entire lifecycle to enable collaboration among different disciplines through an iterative and coordinated exchange of information.

What is the scope? InfraDT will cover concepts and relations related to the representation of physical world objects on the construction site during its lifecycle & the IoT-enabled sensors and their communication to facilitate a state-of-the-art DT platform. It will further provide a basis for the development of specific toolkits quantified in the research project.

Who are the intended end-users? The envisioned end-users include those directly using the ontology such as digital twin technology providers, IoT developers, and digital

solution providers in the construction industry, alongside European standardization bodies. The indirect users could be those primarily involved in the construction industry such as construction managers, construction workers, architects & designers.

3.2 Knowledge Acquisition and Conceptualization

Knowledge acquisition is needed to determine relevant concepts for the ontology and its domain for developing a class hierarchy and setting class properties. Identification of relevant terms is guided by the specification and competency questions presented in the previous section. The acquirement of knowledge is based on literature review, case studies for digital twins in AEC, and brainstorming with project partners. Some literature sources on knowledge capture are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Literature sources for knowledge capturing

Knowledge domain	Source
Digital Twins for Construction	Sacks et al. 2020, Mêda et al. 2021, Boje et al. 2020, Opoku et al. 2022
DT Ontology	Barth et al. 2020, Zheng et al. 2021, El-Diraby 2013, Gregor and Tibaut 2020
Built Environment	ISO 12006, IEC 81346, ETIM 2022
Digital Asset	ISO 19650, CEN 17412, SAREF
Construction phase DT ontology	Calvetti et al. 2020, Boje et al. 2020, Schönbeck et al. 2020, Biccari et al. 2018
Design phase DT ontology	Abou Ibrahim et al. 2022

4 INFRADT

InfraDT conceptualizes the physical and digital assets for an infrastructure digital twin through its entire lifecycle i.e., Design, Construction, and Operation. The conceptualization approach is based on a phase-wise systemization of the lifecycle of an infrastructure's DT. Figure 4 illustrates that each *InfrastructureDigitalTwin* during its lifecycle has a *DesignPhase*, *ConstructionPhase*, and *OperationPhase*. As the development of an ontology representing each phase could result in a complex, large, and probably unpractical approach. Therefore, the InfraDT ontology suite mainly consists of three ontologies DesDT, ConDT, and OpDT for the design, construction, and operation stages respectively for the DT of civil infrastructure.

Figure 4: InfraDT suite with phase-wise lifecycle representation

4.1 Construction DT ontology (ConDT)

The main classes of construction digital twin ontology (ConDT) comprise of general concepts which are common for a construction DT. The concepts illustrated in Figure 5¹ capture the domain knowledge of the digital twin of infrastructure during the construction phase. The *BuiltEnvironment*, *Processes*, and *DigitalAsset* are part of a construction DT and make up the core. Also, the construction DT generates *Outcomes* that can be categorized as the benefits generated due to the implementation of DT during the construction phase. Similarly, the digital twin has *DataResources* which fuel the DT during the construction phase of an infrastructure's lifecycle.

¹ The outlined colors are differentiated to aid the interpretation of the ontology, they do not have a particular meaning in the fig. For all figures representing proposed ontological models, a similar approach with similar colors was implemented.

Figure 5: ConDT ontology and its sub-classes

4.1.1 Built Environment

The *BuiltEnvironment* class conceptualizes basic functional parameters and parts of the built environment existing physically for a construction site and its associated relations. It is based on the IEC/ISO 81346 series of standards (IEC 81346-1, 2009). IEC 81346 aids in the classification of construction elements, where it is stated that each object (built environment in this case) has information associated with it that may change throughout the life cycle of that object. This information has different aspects associated with an object, which are essentially the function, product, and location aspects.

Aspects act like filters on an object (see Figure 6), thus highlighting information of relevance.

- What an object is intended to do or what it actually does – the function aspect;
- By which means an object does what it is intended to do – the product aspect;
- Intended or actual space of the object – the location aspect.

Figure 6: Aspects of an object (IEC 81346)

Figure 7 depicts the *BuiltEnvironment* class and its taxonomical classification with function, product, and location aspects. Subsequently, the sub-classes and their relations are developed based on standard ISO 12006-2 (ISO 12006-2, 2015) describing a framework for the classification of information about construction works. It defines the construction processes, its resources with products and goods, aid, actors, and information. The *FunctionAspect* of a built environment has several sub-classes as illustrated in the ontology.

In the function aspect, the category *ConstructionDocuments* is based on IEC 61355 which describes different document kinds and their attributes. In the IEC 61355 database document kinds are categorized by document kind, identity number, DCC, keyword, application area, activity area, presentation form, and status level. In the international standard IEC 61355-1 the term "document" is used in a very general sense. It covers information on all possible media on which data can be recorded. However, the description of document kinds is derived from the paper-based presentation of this information, i.e., how the information is made visible and readable for the user. The *ConstructionAgent* (human construction resource carrying out a construction process [ISO 12006-2:2015]) can be the client, the designer involved in the planning phase, or the personnel directly involved at the construction site such as contractor, sub-contractor, supplier, fabricator, quality controller & project manager. Construction aids as a resource are intended to assist in carrying out a construction process in the form of tools, installations (formwork/scaffolding), or types of equipment.

When it comes to actual physical aspects of an infrastructure they can be classified as a *ConstructionEntity* (independent unit of the built environment with a characteristic form and spatial structure, intended to serve at least one function or user activity) that can be buildings, highway & railway bridges, or a retaining wall. Which essentially represents types of demo-sites² for the ASHVIN projects including 10 real-life infrastructure projects across Europe. Likewise, a *ConstructionComplex* (aggregate of one or more construction entities intended to serve at least one function or user activity [ISO 12006-2:2015]) can be of several types such as transport, industrial, entertainment, educational, residential, or public health complexes, etc. The *ConstructionElement* sub-class (constituent of a construction entity with a characteristic function, form, or position [ISO 12006-2:2015]) can be possibly a floor, wall, or construction system in case of a building project. With further inclusion of a water supply, power supply, and transportation system in case of an infrastructure project.

The *LocationAspect* class is classified based on the spatial parameters of an infrastructure. It has *BuiltSpaces* which are categorized on basis of the space type. The space type can be for human activity, storage, or infrastructure. In the case of human activity, it can be a living, sanitary, work, production, or gathering space, etc. In terms of spatial representation of a physical structure there can be many relevant sub-classes, but to limit the scope of demonstration for the built environment ontology only the built space sub-class is represented in the ontology.

² <https://www.ashvin.eu/demonstrators/>

Figure 7: BuiltEnvironment class and knowledge blocks for different aspects

Similarly, Figure 9 and Figure 10 represent the products Culvert and Crane respectively. Culvert comes under the civil infrastructure product group and represents a different infrastructure type which is vital as the ASHVIN project includes a diverse portfolio of civil infrastructures. As shown in the figure the *Values* sub-class has different value types which can be A-alphanumeric, L-logic (i.e., yes or no questions), N-numeric value, and R-range (two numeric values that limit a range of values).

Figure 9: Product (Culvert) represent as per ETIM taxonomy

Figure 10: Product (Crane) represent as per ETIM taxonomy

4.1.2 Digital Asset

The *DigitalAsset* is fundamentally the digital representation of the built environment as illustrated in Figure 11. It essentially defines the digital representation parameters of the construction DT. There is a *ProjectInformationModel* which is basically the 3D model representation and the required information of the physical structure existing on the construction site. The class representation of the Information Model is based on the discipline-based federation approach as defined in ISO 19650. The Information Models can be architectural, structural, MEP (mechanical, electrical, plumbing). Also, each BIM model can be described according to the different levels of detail (LOD) describing the precision of a model. Starting from LOD 100 at the pre-design stage consisting of information at the basic level to LOD 400 at the construction stage with complete fabrication, assembly, and detailing information in addition to precise quantity, size, shape, and location.

Additionally, there is a *InformationContainer* that facilitates the exchange of files of a heterogeneous nature by accessing linked information at both object and attribute levels. The information can be *Unstructured* and *Structured*. Unstructured information can be PDF documents, 3D scans, and photos/videos. Each structured information container has *Linkset* and *Dataset*. Similarly, the DT for a construction process uses a different database represented in the form of a *Database* sub-class. The different databases used in the ASHVIN platform are DES (discrete event simulation) and CM (configuration management) databases. It has a *File* sub-class which can be a .ifc, .json, .rvt or a point cloud file (.ply, .xyz, .e57). Along with *Schedules* for project planning and *SensorData* acquired from the installed sensors.

Figure 11: DigitalAsset class representation

The level of information need (LOIN) describes the extent and detail of information exchange in terms of geometry, information, and documentation as shown in Figure

12. The classification of LOIN is based on CEN 17412 (CEN 17412, 2020) describing the information management during the whole life cycle of a built asset. In accordance with this classification LOIN should be described by different concepts: the level of geometry (LOG), level of information (LOI), and documentation (DOC). LOIN identifies the wanted presence of geometry, information, and/or documentation to address a specific purpose at a specified information delivery milestone or agreed date, although it does not describe the status or reliability of the information.

Figure 12: Level of information need framework

Integration of sensors is essential to the DT dynamic behaviour for continuous update of data and information from the physical systems. Each digital asset would have a conceptual representation of the sensors in the form of a *Sensor* class. The *Sensor* class is represented based on existing sensor data ontologies. Current sensor data ontologies such as SSN/SOSA (Haller et al., 2019), SAREF, and QUDT (Cox and Little, 2020) ontology for units of measure and data types provide comprehensive ontological representations and vocabulary of all kinds. The Smart Applications REference ontology (SAREF) and its extension SAREF4BLDG are created based on the IFC standards (Daniele et al., 2015). It is intended to enable knowledge representation for sensor data and sensor systems in buildings. SAREF ontologies provide semantical modelling of the sensor observation process, observed properties as well as the description of sensing devices (see Figure 13). The *Sensor* class here is aligned to SAREF and reusing the class representation is done with the aim of keeping InfraDT extensible.

Figure 13: Overview of SAREF ontology

4.1.3 Data Resources

Data resources are the fuel of every DT application as value creation is not possible without the required data in the needed form. The main subdimensions in the proposed framework are a) the data sources to obtain the data from, b) the data categories they relate to and c) data management for the various processes associated with DT. As shown in Figure 14, the *DataResources* class has seven main concepts named *DataSource*, *DataFormat*, *InputMethod*, *Database*, *DataCategories*, *DataManagement*, and *Owner*. This ontology integrates the dimension of data resources from the ontological framework proposed by Barth et al. (2020) and also incorporates the possible dimensions related to data for a construction DT. The sub-classes *DataFormat* and *InputMethod* show the type of data format (unstructured, structured, interpreted) and the automation level of data collection. Additionally, the data resources can include a *Database* that can consist of relevant standards, historical data, digital building logbooks (DBL), and digital data templates that can augment data-driven construction for the deployment of digital twins (Mêda et al., 2021).

The *DataManagement* sub-class illustrates the whole data lifecycle with data collection, transmission, storage, processing, fusion, and visualization (Qi et al., 2021). Data collection includes static and dynamic status data. Barcodes, QR codes, cameras, sensors, and other IoT technologies are widely used for information identification and real-time perception. Data transmission technologies can include wire and wireless transmission technologies (short-range and long-distance technologies). Both wire and wireless transmissions depend on transmission protocols, access methods, multi-access schemes, channel multiplex modulation, and coding. Thereafter data storage is the technology of storing the collected data for further processing and analysis. Big data storage technologies, such as distributed file storage (DFS), NoSQL database, NewSQL database, and cloud storage are essential for this. Data processing means extracting useful information from a large volume of incomplete, unstructured, noisy, fuzzy, and random raw data. Subsequently, data fusion copes with multisource data through synthesis, filtering, correlation, and integration. Data fusion includes raw-data-level fusion, feature-level fusion, and decision-level fusion which can be done through random methods and artificial intelligence (Qi et al., 2021). Finally, data visualization

serves to present data analysis results in a straightforward, intuitive, and interactive manner. According to the principle of its visualization, these methods can be divided into geometry-based technologies, pixel-oriented technologies, icon-based technologies, layer-based technologies, image-based technologies, etc.

Figure 14: DataResources class and knowledge block for different dimensions

4.1.4 Processes

The *Processes* class essentially represents the processes required to define the workflow for construction centred on digital twins and form the link between the physical structure and the digital model of a construction DT. Figure 15 depicts the relevant processes such as *ConfigurationManagement* to maintain consistency among requirements, design, configured items & associated construction, *ConstructionSimulation* for simulation of construction sequence & activities and *LeanPlanning* to support lean project planning based on DT data.

Figure 15: Processes representation for a construction DT

4.1.4.1 Site Monitoring

To support a DT, a sensed construction site is necessary to monitor construction material, environment, equipment or machines, and workers (Calveti et al., 2020).

Figure 16 conceptualizes the dimensions of the process *SiteMonitoring*. It has various *MonitoringMethods*, which can be a *PortableDevice*, a *WearableDevice* being carried or used by the site personnel while moving through the site. *ImageDevice* can take 2D images (CCTV systems, photographic cameras, UAVs,) and 3D images (LiDAR, point cloud, motion capture systems). *ExternalSensors* are those measuring environmental factors or mechanical factors.

The parameters that can be monitored on a construction site are *Material*, *Environmental*, *Equipment*, and *Worker*. Each dimension has parameters that can be sensed to enable data collection and analysis. Monitoring of equipment through parameters such as Location, State, and Condition facilitates better allocation of resources and optimization of equipment usage.

4.1.4.2 Lean Planning

The Lean Planning process aims to decision making process for lean project planning, control, and risk management with digital twin data. The conceptual representation of lean planning supported by DTs is shown in Figure 17. The lean planning process developed under T4.3 of ASHVIN uses data collected from the site to be evaluated and implemented in the work breakdown structure (WBS) and location breakdown structure (LBS). Therefore, this in combination with the process model allows us to detect issues, react and adjust the schedule.

The process model is developed based on ISO 21500:2012, it includes process groups such as *Initiating*, *Planning*, *Implementing*, *Controlling*, and *Closing*. The planning phase is crucial for successfully and effectively planning and controlling the project. The planning processes are used to conduct detailed planning based on the different Schedules such as work breakdown structure (*WBS*), location breakdown structure (*LBS*), lookahead schedule (*LA*), weekly schedule (*WS*), and daily schedule (*DS*). Subsequently in the implementation phase site data is collected. A vital part of using digital twins to support process management and agile planning is the capture of data from the site through *SiteInput* which can be in various forms (laser scanners, drones, accelerometers, 360 cameras). The *3DModel* is developed in the initiation phase with the required *Geometry* and *Attributes*, which are then mapped to the LBS design using the schedules, and afterward in the implementing phase is used to generate the 4D model to control the project. With the aim to make work ready so that a task can be executed, a number of *Preconditions* or prerequisites for a task have to be planned for and controlled. These prerequisites have a spatial and temporal dimension and are *ConstructionDesign*, *Workers*, *Equipment*, *Space* & *ExternalConditions*. Additionally, the space at the construction site itself can be defined in different subcategories based on the work type as represented in the sub-class *SpaceTypes*.

Figure 16: SiteMonitoring process ontology

Figure 17: Lean Planning process ontology

4.1.4.3 Configuration Management

For the AEC Industry, the use of Configuration Management (CM) provides a means of tracking how the client's expectations generated at the beginning of a project are turned at the completion of the project. The ontological representation of concepts/knowledge for configuration management based on DT data is shown in Figure 18. The Lifecycle class of the CM process has seven fundamental stages in the product lifecycle “as required, as designed, as planned, as built, as used, as demolished” (Biccari et al., 2018). In addition, there are configuration views based on the product structure i.e. the *InformationHierarchy* which is depicted in Figure 18. For instance Product level: building/infrastructure, System level: architecture, electrical, etc., Sub-system level: door, lamp type, etc. The CM process can be subdivided into four major *Elements* namely *ConfigurationPlanning*, *ConfigurationIdentification*, *ConfigurationChangeManagement*, and *ConfigurationVerification* (NASA, 2020). Configuration information has identified five key areas based on ISO 1007: 2017 that can be applicable for construction projects which are Function, Design, Production, Verification & Changes (Schönbeck et al., 2020).

The use of DT data for managing asset configuration data by ensuring trusted information and verification can be vital for the control of construction projects. These verification methods can be through *RFID*, *BluetoothBeacons*, or *DigitalForms* to ensure that information is as per requirements, up-to-date and accessible. Therefore CM is crucial for a digital twin as it provides a complete picture of your physical asset and its configuration data as well as the visual representation to ensure trust.

Figure 18: CM process ontology

4.1.4.4 Risk Management

The process of risk management aims to minimize the chance of structural failure. The issue of structural failure is inextricably linked with the construction industry leading to financial and environmental losses. Risk management includes not only the structural design and its safety, but also project economy, environmental impact, work

environment, and third-party disturbance. For this research risk management focuses on assessing the likelihood of failure occurring and the severity of the consequences. The process presented in Figure 19 gives an overview of the risk assessment procedure for a quay wall structure.

Figure 19: Risk Management ontology

As illustrated in the ontological representation, the design method of used in the risk management assessment can be *Probabilistic*, *Semi-probabilistic* & *Stochastic*. Additionally, it needs to satisfy *DesignConditions* such as the ultimate limit state, service limit state, and/or reliability class. Subsequently, the quay walls are assessed using numerical methods which require *Inputs*, such as *SoilProperties* (soil type, strength, density), *QuayWallGeometry*, and *ConstitutiveModel* for expected soil behavior & *SoilVariability*. Sensors (DT data) are used to indicate the response of structure over time (before, during, and/or after construction) using, for example fibre optics or remote sensing. For a quay wall, the elements monitored include foundation piles, anchors, soil seepage, or diaphragm wall. Eventually, the monitoring data is used to verify the soil property inputs, recalibrate constitutive models, reassess the current structural integrity, and predict future reliability based on changes in loading conditions (e.g. adjustment of dredged depth to accommodate larger ships).

Risk management as a process can be applicable to all three phases of a project (design, construction, and operation). Therefore, many aspects of the risk management ontology can apply to the operation ontology as well, however to appropriately represent WP4 (which has risk management as one of the procedures) of ASHVIN it is included in the ConDT ontology.

4.1.5 Outcomes

There are key performance indicators (KPIs) identified in the ASHVIN project for planning and controlling construction site activities. Therefore, these KPIs are the outcomes/benefits for a DT during the construction phase. Figure 20 illustrates the outcomes generated through DT application enabling productive, resource efficient,

and safe construction. Each outcome (*Productivity*, *ResourceEfficiency*, *Safety*, and *Cost*) has performance indicators (PIs) identified for assessment of the goals. Each sub-class of *Outcomes* has PIs which contributes to its implementation. The PIs were identified to support the implementation during construction works on ASHVIN demonstration projects and ASHVIN tools. The PIs contributing to *Productivity* are productivity rate, remaining work, and target production. *ResourceEfficiency* is governed by the waste factor i.e., the waste accumulated during construction, the number of concurrent trades at the construction site leading to waste of resources, the utilization rate of the site equipment, and space utilization. Similarly, the safety of construction works is determined by factors such as the number of reported issues related to accidents on the site, the safety factor concerning the protection of site workers from harm, and the strength of structural components. Costs for equipment and workers play a decisive part in construction costs.

Figure 20: DT-related outcomes during the construction phase

4.2 Design DT ontology (DesDT)

The DesDT ontology conceptualizes (as shown in Figure 21) aspects that are common for a design phase DT. The main difference between DTs in the construction phase and the design phase is that during design there are no physical dynamics during design such as those happening on site, where sensors can be used to detect changes (Abou Ibrahim et al., 2022). Instead, the design dynamics are happening at the social level on one hand and at the level of the design process on the other hand. However, in this case, the *PhysicalStructure* would be the class that covers the physical aspects of completed projects alongside the parameters for a physical site to be considered for the planning and design phase of an infrastructure project. The other sub-classes such as *Processes* and *Outcomes* would differ from the ConDT ontology. As the different phases of an infrastructure's lifecycle overlap throughout the project, the classes *DataResources*, *PhysicalStructure* & *DigitalModel* are aimed to be kept consistent throughout the lifecycle with some modifications to include parameters relevant for the particular lifecycle phase. Therefore, enabling the exchange of information among phases for the enrichment of a DT-based infrastructure.

Figure 21: DesDT ontology and its classes.

4.2.1 Processes

Figure 22: Processes representation for a DT during the design phase

The *Processes* class principally represents the processes required to define the workflow for design centred on digital twins. Figure 22 outlines the relevant processes for an infrastructure digital twin during the design/planning phase. The processes considered for DesDT ontology are primarily based on WP2 of ASHVIN and other methods for a DT during the design phase. As shown in the ontology the relevant processes such as *Evidence-basedDesign* to develop a design assistant process for future projects based on past projects, *GenerativeDesign* for the development of

different parametric design approaches for design automation, and *DesignInformationDelivery* to support the BIM process with the aim of efficient information delivery and reduction of the overall design process.

4.2.1.1 Evidence-based Design

The process *Evidence-basedDesign* is primarily based on the evidence-based design assistant developed for T2.2 of ASHVIN, which aims to provide a detailed summary of knowledge-based systems along with machine learning for possibilities of recommendation of footbridges aspects for storage of past DT data. The Evidence-based design tool aims to provide insights into aspects like cost, carbon footprint and the likelihood of accidents during the design stage, based on data from previous projects. Figure 23 depicts the concepts and process for an evidence-based design using DTs. To achieve its goal the tool reads design inputs from a *KnowledgeDatabase* that has information from previous evidence of completed projects. Subsequently, the tool uses *MachineLearning* algorithms using a *k-nearestNeighbour* approach to look at footbridges most similar in terms of length and width to the designed one for generating the *Outcomes*. It takes into account various variables such as basic structure & geometry, timeline, design team, financial aspects, and environmental impact, etc. Outcomes are categorized into *Predictions*, *Recommendations*, and *Warnings*. For instance, it computes the likelihood of accidents based on the length and width provided to it, however, it currently does take into account aspects such as average wind speeds at the construction site that may impact the likelihood of accidents. The accuracy of the predictions is conditioned by the accuracy of the data. Variables such as cost and duration of public projects may often be accurate, others such as the prevalence of accidents may often rely on the willingness of construction companies to disclose that data. Although with imperfect data, insights, and recommendations the tool won't provide a comprehensive decision, the use of an Evidence-based design tool will be enhanced than a random guess.

Figure 23: Overview of the ontology for evidence-based design.

4.2.1.2 Generative Design

The conceptual representation of the process generative design is based on T2.3 of ASHVIN. The parametric model uses the information provided by the *Evidence-basedDesign* tool (GEN). Furthermore, the GEN tool comprises of both *ParametricModelling* and *GenerativeDesign* aspects, thus having a two-fold purpose. Parametric modeling generates the initial design used as a surrogate for the generative design as portrayed in Figure 24. It has *HistoricData*, *TacitKnowledge*, and *ParametricLogic&Algorithms* that generate a parametric model. Historic data is based on established data with *Dimensions* of existing physical structures, project records, and standards, whereas tacit knowledge is based experience of field experts. The parametric model is a developed 'skeletal model' with sliders whose limits are numerical ranges (extents of features based on past project experiences for example) of key parameters for the structures which can be designed. For example, in this case, for our demonstration renovation project, it would be the widths, lengths, and heights of the windows.

For *GenerativeDesign* the parametric model developed then provides a surrogate initial design (*SurrogateParametricModel*) for generating various design alternatives based on the Optimization algorithm *FitnessFunctions*. The optimization algorithms use the non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm (NSGA) to evaluate the objectives within specified ranges (of minimum and maximum limits). Additionally, the *Objective* is based on the KPIs (productivity, cost, resource efficiency) and the PIs set for the particular project. *VariableParameters* have changeable values that can be varied within the project constraints. The *Constraints* are limitations such as *MaximumParameter* (e.g., the length between connection points for bridge) and *MaximumStautoryProvisions* (e.g., the distance of window from next building). Thus, based on the generative *DesignAlternatives* are generated that can be evaluated, visualized and ranked based on suitable performance criteria. Therefore, the generative design process is handy to help AEC designers in the early design phase to quickly generate different possible options for a project design for intelligible decision-making to select the most suitable option for construction planning and development.

Figure 24: Generative design process ontology

4.2.1.3 4D Planning Visualization

The 4D planning visualization for design (4DV-D) process based on T2.4 of ASHVIN aims to provide a comparison of design alternatives according to the established KPIs. The 4DV-D tool uses the *DesignVariants* created by the generative design tool as input consisting of the different *ParametricModels* with their respective *KPIScores* and *FitnessFunctions*. Based on the input the tool creates 4D *Visualization* of the design alternatives. Which primarily has the *3DModel* of the project, the Multi-viewport feature for the 3D environment to facilitate the comparison of design alternatives, and *ParametricVariables* to change the geometric parameters of the uploaded 3D model to analyze various possibilities. Based on the visualization the 4DV-D aids the designers in understanding the ramifications of their design choices. The planning part of the 4DV-D tool will be visualized and analyzed on an associated *Dashboard* with different *DesignAlternatives* for meaningful comparisons and their *Predictions* based on the concerning KPIs of productivity, cost, resource efficiency, and safety.

Figure 25: 4DV-D process ontology

4.2.2 Outcomes

Structural design is an experience-based, rational, but also a creative process that has been supported by a collection of data and experience. A new aspect of the approach presented here is the clear structuring and the data-supported holistic consideration of the most diverse aspects of the design. For the research study, the development of KPIs and PIs was based on past footbridge projects during the maintenance phase. The assessment of a design is reduced to a few representative criteria and associated key figures. The outcomes generated through DT-based structural design outcomes during the design phase are depicted in Figure 26. The outcome relevant to the design of engineering projects is mapped to four pre-defined KPIs (*Productivity*, *ResourceEfficiency*, *Health&Safety*, and *Cost*). *Productivity* related PIs contributing to the outcomes are *PersonnelProductivity* giving the overall design/engineering man-hours, the *StructuralAdequacy* defining the ability of a structure to withstand design

loads, *StructuralRedundancy* to determine if the structure is structurally redundant based on continuity within the load path, and so on. The PIs identified for *ResoureEfficiency* represent resource efficiency and sustainability-related performance indicators, most of which are indicators of life cycle and environmental impact indicators as defined in Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) databases. PIs determining the *Health&Safety* outcome are represented based on different footbridges as references such as *Comfort*, *NoOfAccidents*, and *IncidentRate*. Performance indicators related to *Cost* and Revenue are material cost and personnel cost, *PaybackPeriod* indicates the time taken to cover costs and is usually considered to asses risks.

Whereas the four KPIs criteria are essential, they are too restrictive and inhibit the assessment of a good structural design. Design aspects such as structure & design, functionality, comfort, and sustainability are ignored in the selected key performance indicators. Additionally, aspects of other structures apart from pedestrian bridges can be incorporated.

Figure 26: DT-based outcomes during the design phase

4.3 Operation DT ontology (OpDT)

The ontology OpDT represents the operation/maintenance phase of a built infrastructure centered on digital twins (as depicted in Figure 27). This phase of an infrastructure’s lifecycle is the longest and in most cases the most vital phase of the lifecycle. Therefore, in this case, the *PhysicalStructure* would represent the completed structure along with added aspects for the operation & maintenance of that structure. Also, other classes *Processes* and *Outcomes* represent the process and the benefits of the DT.

Figure 27: OpDT ontology and its classes.

4.3.1 Processes

For the OpDt ontology, the *Processes* class primarily represents the necessary processes for a built infrastructure’s DT during the operation & maintenance phase. The processes (see Figure 28) considered for OpDT ontology are primarily based on WP5 of ASHVIN and other relevant methods for a DT during the operation phase. The significant process is *StructuralHealthMonitoring* (SHM) to demonstrate the use of DTs for damage detection and assessment of civil engineering infrastructures like bridges, tunnels, and airport runways. *Multi-physicsCalibration* to simulate and calibrate models to represent the realistic state of the physical asset. *PerformancePrediction* for risk-based predictive maintenance and *EnergyManagement* for improvement and optimization of energy consumption for buildings. *Decision-MakingSystem* involves humans (the users) to make the final decision based on real-time data.

Figure 28: Processes representation for a DT during the maintenance/operation phase

4.3.1.1 Structural Health Monitoring (SHM)

The primary requirement from the SHM system to DT is the possibility to match structural monitoring systems to the digital model and to deploy sensor data visualizations onto the BIM model to digitally replicate the SHM system. Likewise, the DT would require from the SHM the actual site condition and tools for analysis. Thus Figure 29 gives an overview of the structural health monitoring process using digital twins. A typical SHM system contains three main elements: a sensor system, a data processing system, and a health evaluation system.

A *SensorSystem* generally contains three components (1) a measuring device i.e. *Device*, (2) a method of sensing/measuring i.e. *Method*, and (3) a way of storing the sensed data i.e. *Storage*. A *DataProcessingSystem* consists of data acquisition, transmission, aggregation, processing, and storage). The health evaluation system would essentially use the processed data for the evaluation of the structure’s health. The system can vary depending on the sensors and data acquisition system alongside the requirements for the structural performance assessment. The method can be surface damage detection, evaluation of the crack formation & monitor the crack propagation, and monitoring of pile settlement for bridges.

Figure 29: DT-based SHM ontology

4.3.1.2 Multi-Physics Calibration

DT-enabled multi-physics simulation provides the required phenomenological insight for the calibration of virtual models. The multi-physics model calibration process utilizes DT data through sensors for developing numerical simulations and subsequently calibrating the digital model to represent real asset behavior as portrayed in the ontology (see Figure 30). The DT-data is obtained through *Sensors* which can be through various measurements such as *LVDT* & *Infermometer* to simulate load tests or *Thermocouples* for energy simulations. The DT data is used for the *Simulation* of different physical processes for infrastructure (can be mechanical, fluid, or thermal processes). The simulation can be for multiphysics processes such as *FEM* (finite element modeling), *CFD* (computational fluid dynamics) simulation, *BEM* (building energy modeling), *LoadTest* for bridges, or *SolarShading* analysis. Also, the simulation method can be numerical, experimental, or theoretical. For the numerical models, it can be based on *Reduced-orderMethods* aimed at establishing computationally tractable real-time simulations and *Full-orderMethods* aimed at establishing a detailed state of the asset. Thus, the simulation of realistic conditions would facilitate the *Calibration* of the virtual model to be subsequently used for multi-criteria system evaluations through the *Evaluation*.

Figure 30: DT-based Multiphysics ontology

4.3.2 Outcomes

Asset management and maintenance for civil infrastructures using DTs aim to define optimal maintenance strategies in order to ensure the fulfillment of the desired performance level. Therefore, these outcomes/performance levels are assessed with KPIs and PIs. Figure 31 demonstrates the outcomes generated through DT application enabling productive, resource efficient, safe, and cost-efficient maintenance and operation of infrastructure. The outcomes of DT application during the operation phase are based on identified KPIs (*Productivity*, *ResourceEfficiency*, *Health&Safety*, and *Cost*), wherein each has its own PIs. The PIs determined are based on WP5 of ASHVIN in which the types of infrastructure primarily considered were high-speed railway bridge (demo#1), airport runway (demo#3), and highway bridge network (demo#7).

The PIs contributing to *Productivity* are *DurationofWorks*, *PrefabricationLevels* i.e., product readiness when delivered to site, *StrPerformance*, and *ServiceLife* of the maintenance work carried out. For highway and railway infrastructure projects, they can have additional PIs such as *TrafficIntensity* and *ClousureLanes*. *ResoureEfficiency* is dependent on *EnergyConsumption*, *Recyclability*, and *Reusability* i.e., whether the structure or part of a structure used for certain maintenance can be recycled or reused after a certain time or end of life along with *EnvironmentallImpacts* of maintenance works, machines, and materials. Likewise, health & safety is determined by *ConditionRating* (degree of damage expressed by an index), *ReliabilityIndex* (Probability of failure and failure mode) along with other health-based and safety factors for workers and the infrastructure users. Performance indicators related to *Cost* are *MaintenanceCost* related to maintenance activities, *TotalLCC* for life cycle costs of maintenance and repair activities including direct & indirect costs, and *EnvironmentalCost* for instance costs related to traffic congestion during maintenance work (CO2 emission).

Figure 31: DT-based outcomes during the operation/maintenance phase

5 ONTOLOGY EVALUATION

This section illustrates the evaluation process of the current version of InfraDT, in which a description is given of the ontology evaluation approaches applied in this study, and the results of the evaluation are presented. For this deliverable, the evaluation was done only for the ConDT ontology as it is more comprehensively developed in comparison to DesDT and OpDT ontologies.

5.1 Workshop with experts

El-Gohary and El-Diraby (2010) emphasize the importance of domain expert participation in ontology evaluation, as the evaluation requires judgment on abstraction, classification, and coverage based on given domain knowledge. When developing the InfraDT ontology, expert evaluation workshops were conducted within the ASHVIN consortium to assess the ontology content and identify potential modifications from the user's point of view. The goal was to ensure whether the ontology is coherent with aspects of a construction digital twin of civil infrastructure. The specific questions were evaluated for the verification:

- Does the model cover all the concepts and attributes required to fulfill its intended use?
- Does the taxonomy and hierarchy of concepts represent the terms and structure of the elements in the real world?
- Are the relations between concepts according to real-world interactions?

The ontology specification and overall brief of the ontology were presented to the experts, after which the general model and details of each concept were introduced. Subsequently, an analysis of the comments and results was done to adjust the ontology, the following adjustments were made:

- To change the name of the class from *PhysicalStructure* to *BuiltEnvironment* for the physical representation of an infrastructure. Primarily because a built environment encompasses more parameters for the construction site in comparison to a physical structure which only represent the physical infrastructure e.g.: bridge, building, etc.
- Likewise, the name of the class *DigitalModel* was changed to *DigitalAsset* for a more comprehensive representation of the virtual parameter of an infrastructure's digital twin. Alongside further recommendations to use standards such as ISO 19650 to incorporate the federated approach for developing the ontologies for BIM models.
- To create an aspect-based concept for the *BuiltEnvironment* class for the hierarchy based on the industry standard IEC 81346 that aids in the classification of construction elements. This approach enriches the classification of the *BuiltEnvironment* class based on the idea that each element of a built environment has information associated with it based on different aspects which will be essential for the architecture of the ASHVIN DT platform.
- Make use of industry-standard ETIM classification for the classification of the *ProductAspect* sub-class. As it has already well-defined 19102 products & tools used during construction or the construction related process. Also, ETIM

as a format allows to share and exchange of product data based on taxonomic identification.

5.2 Ontology design verification

The final ConDT ontology model was implemented in the form OWL/RDF in Protégé. Protégé is the most widely used software with many advanced features for building and maintaining OWL ontologies (Musen and the Protégé Team, 2015). As a standard process, the final ontologies are checked thoroughly to validate the concepts' description, their hierarchy, object properties, data properties, and the relations between them. For the verification process, the final ontological models implemented using OWL/RDF in Protégé are reviewed extensively, the hierarchy is revisited and the relations of each class and sub-class are checked. Certain parameters are used to check the models in the form of a common list of errors made during the ontological development process as presented below:

- A class is defined as a sub-class and super-class at the same time
- Excessive use of the isA property (ontological structure with a merely classificatory approach)
- Incomplete existing classes
- Non-disjoint classes
- Lack of exhaustivity
- Concepts or terms represented multiple times

ConDT ontology was reviewed through a list of common errors presented above. The review process is summarized in Table 2. Adjustments were implemented to solve the errors identified, some of them are mentioned in the table

Table 2: Errors for the ConDT ontology verification

Description	Related Error
The hasLocationAspect property was defined but not linked to the Domain and Range	Lack of specification and limitation of the properties
The class DataCategories was not disjoint with the rest of the sibling classes	Non-disjoint classes
Adjustment: The properties hasCost and hasProductivity were assigned to the class BuiltEnvironment	Lack of specification and limitation of the properties
The sub-classes from the class ProductAspect were not disjoint	Non-disjoint classes
The sub-classes from the sub-classes DataManagement were not disjoint	Non-disjoint classes
Adjustment: Sub-properties for the object property hasFunctionAspect were created to define this relation better and facilitate use in the model	Lack of specification and limitation of the properties

6 STRUCTURED VOCABULARY AND APIS

Structured vocabularies as means of defining and structuring the meanings of concepts and terms are essential to ensure consistency through the lifecycle of construction. In their digital, machine-readable form they can be used in the digital twin context to extract geometrical data from the construction site for visualization purposes for semantic simulation of a construction site in the DT and interoperability in data exchange scenarios (Beetz, 2018). As per the intended use, structured vocabularies and classification systems can be created in different forms. Shared dictionaries can be used to transfer multiple languages into simple data models that can be used in automation scenarios. Nomenclatures, glossaries, and terminologies as basic forms of shared vocabularies consist of commonly agreed technical terms, and their definitions are arranged in some order e.g., alphabetically. Thus, a translation of these dictionaries without hardcoding terms into user interfaces can be stored as natural language terms in separate dictionaries and added to the tool dynamically at runtime. Similarly, ontologies can be used to represent several relation types and aspects in a common model. In fully-fledged ontologies, relations are often used that are rarely represented based on principles provided by formal logic, thus making it possible to draw conclusions (inferences) based on statements or facts (axioms) (Beetz, 2018). The set of information about a specific controlled terminology term is designated as term metadata, whereas an ontology on the other hand, is a formal representation of a domain knowledge where concepts are organized hierarchically.

An ontology defines mappings from properties in formats to a common set of properties. Additionally, the API (Application programming interface) would define methods to access heterogeneous metadata using such mappings. Under the WP1 of ASHVIN, the deliverable D1.4 related to T1.3 develops a set of IDM (Information Delivery Manual) for the ETL process of various ASHVIN tools, along with APIs for the purpose of describing the reference pivot model for interoperability. The report mainly describes the interoperability requirements for WP4 (construction phase) to enable communication between the ASHVIN systems. The APIs developed for ASHVIN architecture are summarized in Table 3. The integration of the APIs developed in the InfraDT ontology would enable interoperability within the ASHVIN architecture. Some of the APIs developed have already been modeled in the ontology developed. Also, existing research on the development of a data model for a digital twin in the construction phase to represent activities holistically and use construction information to fulfill performance indicators can provide already developed vocabulary and hierarchy for future development (Schlenger, 2021).

Table 3: Construction DT Interoperability APIs

API	Description
/activities	Returns a list of activities
/pastactivities	Returns a list of activities completed and running to the current date.
/environmentalconditions/{activityID}	Get the possible environmental conditions that might influence an activity
/pdf/{activityID}/{environmentalconditionID}	Get a probability density function (pdf) for an activity
/schedulescenarios	Returns the scheduled scenarios

/constructionElement	Returns a list of construction elements
/requirements/{constructionelementID}	Returns a list of requirements for a construction element
/componentstatus/{requirementID}	Gets the automatically calculated status of a construction element's requirement
/kpis	Gets all KPIs for the project
/safetykpis	Gets all Safety related KPIs for the project

All the APIs described have schemas and mainly cater to the tools in WP4 tools - (DES: Simulation-based real-time construction site and logistics planning tool), (CMT: Configuration management tool to track as-designed and as-built to track requirements and for seamless commissioning), (4DV-C: Tool for 4d simulation past construction activities with the associated KPIs) and (SMT: safety management tool). Under the *Process* subclass of the ConDT ontology, the ontologies of these tools have been developed as processes to conceptualize the knowledge, data, and other relevant parameters. Therefore, the integration of the APIs of respective tools in the ontological model of the respective tools would provide the respective tool developers with an understanding of the knowledge domain and information flow. Likewise using the ontologies as a reference to generate vocabularies for APIs, through generic controlled vocabularies will be significant to link metadata for the ASHVIN DT platform.

7 CONCLUSION

The cross-phase data flow between design, construction, and maintenance within the framework of a digital twin, as envisaged in the ASHVIN project, can help to strengthen this data and information flow between the individual protagonists of a project. Therefore, the ontological models presented here are a potential starting point to initiate the development of digital twins of built/civil infrastructure through the entire lifecycle from design to operation. This deliverable details the methodology and concepts used to develop the InfraDT ontology suite. The ontological representation and the knowledge specification are in alignment with the specification and requirements of ASHVIN architecture.

Currently, the InfraDT ontology consists of three main ontologies ConDT, DesDT & OpDT for the construction, design, and operation/maintenance phases respectively. For this research study, the development of construction phase ontology ConDT was prioritized as the ASHVIN project had more resources in terms of demo sites, toolkits, and DT data from this phase. Therefore, ConDT was developed to conceptualize a construction digital twin along with its physical objects (with required attributes) & their virtual replica essentially for the digital twining of an infrastructure's construction process. Furthermore, the DesDT & OpDT ontologies are presented in the deliverable with the conceptualization of the processes, tools & KPIs catering to these phases of the infrastructure lifecycle respectively.

During the implementation of *BuiltEnvironment* and *DigitalAsset* classes, the use of existing relevant standards was prioritized such as ISO 12006, IEC 81346, IEC 61355, ISO 19650 & ISO 21500 to support European standardization bodies for DT standard development and use of the hierarchical & logical taxonomy developed in these standards. Also, the coverage analysis to identify potential knowledge representation/conceptualization aspects not covered by the current version of the ontology such as: the IoT platform, connectivity of sensor with the IoT platform, its integration with the DT platform, and the security and privacy requirements of the ASHVIN DT Platform as per industry needs.

Therefore, the InfraDT ontology suite alongside knowledge representation and conceptualization would aid the sharing and interoperability among the different toolkits, and components of ASHVIN architecture, for the development of the DT platform with the aim of demonstrating the platform services on the demo sites of the project.

8 OUTLOOK

The proposed approach will evolve, as the development of the DT in terms of applicability is still at the outset and research along with real cases in the particular area are just emerging. Thus, the addition of new dimensions or refining the definition outlined in this paper is highly plausible. From the perspective of future studies, the following aspects will be considered:

- Build upon the work done for design (DesDT) and operation phase (OpOnt) ontologies for further enrichment of the particular phases alongside ensuring representation of overlapping information between all the lifecycle phases.
- Ontologies developed in this task will be visualized on a web application (e.g., WebVOWL) for interactive visualization of ontologies, thus providing graphical depictions for elements by combining with a force-directed graph layout. The InfraDT ontology portal will serve as a live repository for the different ontologies, hence containing the latest version of the developed ontologies and related artifacts.
- Further development on a structured common vocabulary for the ontologies will be established in association with the created APIs to facilitate interoperability among different elements/toolkits of the ASHVIN architecture, in particular the communication with the DT platform.
- The next steps will also be devoted to collecting more ontological requirements from the demo sites to iteratively evolve the InfraDT ontology suite for the instantiation of respective demo cases.

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APPENDIX- ONTOLOGIES HIERARCHY AND PROPERTIES

ConDT Ontology hierarchy

The complete hierarchy of ConDT ontology extracted from the model developed in Protégé is shown in Figure 32 and Figure 33.

Figure 32: ConDT ontology hierarchy 1

Figure 33: ConDT ontology hierarchy 2

ConDT property hierarchies

Figure 34 illustrates the object property hierarchies of the ConDT ontology.

Figure 34: Object property hierarchies

Standards

The section summarizes the standard, norms & regulations used in the research study to inform ontology development.

- IEC 81346-1:2022 *Industrial systems, installations and equipment and industrial products – Structuring principles and reference designations – Part 1: Basic rules*
- IEC 81346-2:2022 *Industrial systems, installations and equipment and industrial products – Structuring principles and reference designations – Part 2: Classification of objects and codes for classes*
- ISO 12006-2:2015 *Building Construction – Organization of information about construction works – Part2: Framework for classification*
- CEN 17412-1:2020 *Building Information Modelling – Level of Information Need – Part1: Concepts and principles*
- ISO 19650-1:2018 *Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modeling (BIM) – Information management using building information modeling – Part 1: Concepts and principles*
- IEC 61355-1:2008 *Classification and designation of documents for plants, systems, and equipment – Part 1: Rules and classification tables*
- ISO 55000:2014 *Asset management – Overview, principles, and terminology*
- ETIM International Classification *A international classification standard for technical products. ETIM allows for technical products to be classified and uniformly described by product groups, classes, synonyms, features, values and units.*